

AN OVERVIEW OF THE RELATIONSHIP MODEL OF MARRIED COUPLES IN BUILDING SEXUAL COMMUNICATION RELATIONS IN INDONESIA

SANTI DELLIANA¹, AHMAD SIHABUDDIN², and MIKHAEL DUA³

¹Sahid University and Institut Teknologi dan Bisnis Kalbis, Indonesia.

²Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa University, Indonesia.

³Atma Jaya Catholic University, Indonesia.

Abstract

The communication skills of married couples have a major impact on sexual and relationship satisfaction. It is unimaginable if a husband and wife do not have communication skills and remain silent without communication and then live together in a household for a long period of time. Obviously, such conditions would be unpleasant. These kinds of issues commonly arise in relationships between husband and wife. This study seeks to identify a model of the communication interaction between a husband and wife. This study employs a qualitative approach method, along with an Analysis of Interpretive Phenomenology (AFI). The findings highlight the dialectic in interpersonal relationships between husband and wife, interpersonal relationships that are established to pursue a common goal, mutual benefits, and other advantages. This interpersonal relationship is said to be unique because it contains contradictions or tensions that often occur in interpersonal relationships. The relationship model for husband and wife in building sexual communication relations has the following elements: in autonomy and connection the elements are Autonomy, Care, Duration of communication, Relationship process, Problem Solving, Sharing, and Connection.

Keywords: Relationship Model, Sexual Communication, Couples

1. INTRODUCTION

Based on the goal stated in Article 1 of Law Number 1 of 1974, namely to form a happy and eternal family (household) based on Belief in One Almighty God, it was clear that the harmonization of husband and wife relations was vital in order to achieve the goal of marriage. The aim of marriage was to bring happiness, love, satisfaction, and offspring. Husband and wife who married with defined goals in mind always seek to have a happy family (Melinda & Prihartanti, 2013). In order to limit the number of widowed couples and young men, it is essential that marriages should not be performed too early for reasons of age and maturity (Delliana, 2021). Family communication has various facets as a component of building harmonious interactions for all communication parties engaged in it, and it influences the development of warm and happy relationships between family members (Kaddi et al., 2020). However, communication breakdowns were the main cause of marital dissatisfaction (Prochaska & DiClemente, 2005). Most arguments between husband and wife were caused by communication problems. This phenomenon was not only experienced by married couples with decades of marriage ties, husband and wife who had married also often experience failure in communication. Further, according to Prochaska and DiClemente (2005), the cause of

communication failure also was due to the couple's tendency of easily blaming their partner (blaming partner), even though what the partner did was clearly not wrong. Communication breakdowns were sparked by both parties responding incorrectly to each other (Wulandari & Rahmi, 2018).

In this relation, previous studies have found that satisfaction and sexual pleasure has a significant relationship. Partner relationship satisfaction has a significant influence on higher in sexual activity (Mackey et al., 2000). An important part of the marital relationship was the sexual relationship between partners. This part of the marital relationship has an effective role towards marital satisfaction. Generally, a low level of sexual relations was a straight line with a high level of marital conflict (Sadeghi & Samani, 2011). The background of couples who had sexual communication failure does not only involve the partner's sexual identity, but touches on key elements of partner intimacy. In this sense, men and women have different perspectives on sexual relations. For men, sex and love might be two separate things that couldn't be combined, but for women, they were two attributes that belong related (Blow & Hartnett, 2005). Healthy sexuality was an important part of human life as a component of psychological fulfillment (Dosch et al., 2016) and relationship satisfaction (Byers, 2005). In order to build a harmonious relationship, changes in sexual satisfaction in the form of positive and negative aspects were crucial (Byers, 2005). In general, previous researchers have found the importance of physically expressing husbands and wives, who can communicate positively about conflict and love, with levels of relationship satisfaction (Mackey et al., 2000).

Table 1: Percentage of Households by Region of Residence, Age Group, Gender of Head of Household, and Marital Status, 2009-2021

Area of Residence	Age Group of the Household's Head	2021				
		Single	Married	Divorced	Widower/Widow	Total
urban areas	10-24	91,05	4,64	4,23	0,08	100,00
	25-44	19,89	21,89	35,81	22,42	100,00
	45-59	3,69	8,95	21,06	66,29	100,00
	60+	1,86	2,69	6,05	89,40	100,00
	Total	10,78	8,23	16,13	64,85	100,00

According to Jones, Robinson & Seedall (2018), sexual frequency and orgasm were indicators of how sexual communication affects sexual satisfaction and relationships. Further, they suggest that it was necessary to doing more research to better understand qualitatively the basic differences between communications in general and sexual communication with a better explanation. Meanwhile, Jones; Frederick, Lever, Gillespie & Gracia (2017) highlight that although there was previous literature on sexual satisfaction, it turns out that measuring sexual satisfaction was very complex. In this case, sexual satisfaction not only seen from the satisfaction itself but also how couples could maintain sexual arousal throughout the relationship. As such, they suggest further research on techniques to increase decreased sexual arousal and how couples still spend time together to build intimacy. As can be seen in Table 1, the data showed that in urban areas with divorced marital status, 35, 81% of the 25-44 age group and 21, 06% of the 45-59 age group. In this regard, several factors causing divorce in

Indonesia was revealed which includes disputes, economics factor, leaving one party, domestic violence, and polygamy. Disputes that occur in married couples were generally related to each other's egoism. Usually, there was an issue that continues to be brought up and occurs repeatedly. Lack of communication due a lot of busyness, which lead to silence on partner, and talking at the wrong time could affect the relationship, causing unhappiness (Annur, 2022a, 2022b; Badan Pusat Statistik, 2021; Pengadilan Agama Bojonegoro, 2022; Rahmawati, 2019).

Considering the context, there was a gap between the issue of sexual dissatisfaction in marriage and the absence of study regarding sexual communication in husband-wife relationships, which makes this research significant. Indonesians value relationship development in marriage even though understanding of sexual expression and sexual communication was still very minimal. Developing sexual communication techniques used by partners would be the first step towards the productive exchange of ideas in this study. Ideally, current findings will enrich our understanding of the exploration of sexual communication. After becoming married, partners are supposed to have a more developed grasp of how to communicate sexually with one another. On the other hand, not every couple shares the same level of knowledge in sexual communication. Because of the critical nature of this research, it was carried out in order to investigate sexual communication, which is something that ought to be an area of knowledge for a couple. This study aims to identify a model of the relationship between husband and wife in establishing sexual communication relations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Interpersonal Communication

The term relationship was used to talk about very close (intimate) friendly relations. In emotional connection and sexual intimacy was basically involved (emotional and sexual intimacy). Relationships between teachers and students, parents and children, employers, staff or between doctors and patients, and husbands and wives were often used for social unit purposes.

However, in the most basic sense, a relationship was formed, as reported by Ruben & Stewart (2006) "a relationship is formed whenever reciprocal processing occurs, that is, when two or more individuals mutually take account of and adjust to one another's verbal or nonverbal behavior" (Brent & Lea, 2006, p. 244), when mutual message processing occurs. There were relationships that were based on the processing of mutual messages, which were called interpersonal relationships. For communication theorists, interpersonal relationships were usually referred to as interpersonal contacts.

2.2 Communication Psychology

Communication psychology refers to a branch of research that draws on the power of psychology and sociopsychology to examine how people interact and communicate as social beings. Based on psychological research, communication psychology studies interpersonal relationships and communication patterns between people. The psychology of communication

can shed light on a variety of social contexts in which a person's personality plays an important role, in which a person's judgments may be biased because of one's own beliefs and emotions, and in which a person can exercise influence over others (Morissan, 2016). Couples might improve their ability to communicate with one another and even prepare themselves for potential future conflicts through the use of self-assessment (Widaningsih, 2011).

2.3 Body Communication

Humans interpret and define one another's activities in the course of interaction. It was more than a simple reaction to one's conduct toward others. A person's response to the activities of others was not directly dependent on those actions, but rather on the "meaning" attributed to those behaviors (Sihabudin, 2019). Body Communication means communicated through movement. While humans generally accept this premise from time to time, they seldom investigate its consequences in detail. If movement conveys meaning, then various movements perform various communication tasks by conveying various meanings. Certain meanings conveyed by physiological signals assist us in achieving certain communicative goals, whereas others express deep dysfunctional meanings (Eaves & Leathers, 2018).

2.4 Nature of Body Signals

Much like facial expressions, body gestures have been conceptualized as categorical and dimensional in nature. The categorical perspective was based on the assumption that sign bodies were best understood by classifying them with respect to: (a) the level of awareness and intention used; (b) the type of coding used; and (c) the communicative functions served. In contrast, a dimensional perspective was based on the assumption that body cues were best explained by rating them on a scale that represents the dimension of meaning communicated by body cues. The theory and research of Ekman (1992) best describes the categorical perspective, while the dimensional perspective is most closely related to the work of Mehrabian (1996). Thorough and recent essays provide a complete review of some kinesis literature and applications for use in everyday life (Dael et al., 2016).

2.5 Sexual Communication

Communication of a sexual nature within the context of an established relationship. The phrase sexual communication was used frequently in both academic and popular discourse to refer to the many forms of expression seen in committed relationships (such as dating and marriage) that led to mutual sexual pleasure. This research has mostly concentrated on two topics: the sexual terms or vocabulary partners use when discussing sex, and the types of communication skills that were required to accomplish mutually satisfying sexual activity.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach method. This study uses phenomenology accompanied by an Analysis of Interpretive Phenomenology (AFI) or an Analysis of Interpretational Phenomenology. The interpretive approach was based on attempts to describe social or cultural phenomena based on the views and perceptions of the people being studied (Dua, 2020). The

interpretive approach was taken from a realistic point of view. The interpretive approach was generally a social structure with an overarching and direct interpretation of action (Liliweri, 2018). As for the assumptions of Ontology, Epistemology, Methodology, Axiology and Rhetoric in the constructivist paradigm in this research (Ronda, 2022). The research was carried out in Jakarta. The author chose Jakarta because Jakarta serves as Indonesia's barometer in the eyes of the international community.

The sample was determined using the cluster random sampling method after the homogeneity test was carried out and the population was declared homogeneous (Albab & Astutik, 2021). The cluster random sampling approach was a regional sampling methodology used to select a sample size when the items examined were very large, such as people from a country, province, or district (Astaman et al., 2020; Sugiyono, 2013). Exploratory research was also carried out in new research areas whose research objectives were:

1. Knowing the extent, degree, problem or behavior of a particular phenomenon.
2. An initial idea (or gut feeling) about the phenomenon was generated.
3. Check if a wider study of this phenomenon was possible.

The data collection technique taken was ethnographic interviews. Data collection began in October 2019 and lasted until the couples decided in January 2020. We requested correspondence or statements from Universitas Sahid to facilitate interviews with each partner.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The subjects were chosen based on the author's criteria, which included 5 (five) husband and wife pairs and a total of 10 (ten) people. The presentation of the 5 pairs of research subject profiles was included using pseudonyms to maintain the confidentiality of the informants. There were also various struggle, tensions, or differences in a relationship that may have an impact on the relationship.

4.1 Autonomy and Connection

The dialectic of autonomy and attachment refers to our ever-present desires to become independent of those who were important to us, and also to seeks intimacy with them. Even though there are many similarities, there is always a desire not to depend on others (Mary Anne Fitzpatrick in (Budyatna, 2011). In fact, "independence" from this relationship still assumes a need for intimacy amid a wish to not be dependent on a partner (West & Turner, 2004). Relationships characterized by tension/conflict between individuals. Communication patterns in a relationship that cause tension were defined by Baxter (1988) on (West & Turner, 2017). The result of conflicting emotional needs felt by members of any relationship was tension. This tension exists not only when the children were married but also when they were unmarried, as Bexter points out. However, such tension would increase when the child gets married but still lives with his parents. This happens because in the family system, each family member has a different role. Family roles were repetitive patterns of behavior that arise from the interactions of family members to fulfill family functions (Galvin et al., 2004). The roles played in the

family system keeps the family system running smoothly (Galvin et al., 2004). As a result, when the roles and functions of family members overlap, family tensions increase. The child's husband or wife would take over the father's role as the head of the family and the mother as caregiver. On the other hand, parents continued to play this role as long as the child lives with them, even if the child married. According to the preceding theory, the tension could be seen in the contradictions that we often experience. To begin with, predictability-newness, which was the contradiction in that family members were used to constant and repetitive activities - those activities that felt very familiar - but they seek new challenges that could be used as experiences or even changes. In this case, we saw this inconsistency when the attitudes and behavior of children changed after they got married.

Changes in the status of children and the arrival of new family members cause this shift in attitudes and behavior. Several factors affect a person's attitude and behavior. There was the influence of parents, friends, and the social environment as well as the influence of the partner once the child enters the marriage period. The four forming factors, namely family, school, peers, and the surrounding community affects a person's behavior (Sarlito, 2012). On the other hand, marriage cannot be denied in its ability to affects children's behavior. According to Sandi in (Utami, 2016) married life requires adjustment with a partner.

Figure 1: Autonomy and Connection

The first couples apply system budget in financial management. The wife was given a daily ration of money. However, the wife does not always feel that she has to rely on her husband's allotment of money. The wife tries to find additional income to add to the allotment of money she receives. There was dependence on money rations from husbands but there was also a growing attitude of independence by seeking other sources of income.

“You know... I don't look like wives in general... those who don't have enough money and complain at their husband... I never make demands, if I want to buy a thing, I try myself...” (Interview Wife 1).

Even though the wife was a private employee with a fixed income, Husband 3 was still trying to find a better job in order to increase his income. As a husband, there was no apparent dependence on the wife who has a steady income.

“yes, for example, the finances are not balanced, because of what, at that time I did not get a good job, so what it turns out is that we have to have car payments that are quite high and that is the reason we are short of money, but after that the third year it has started to stabilize until now” (Husband Interview 3).

The marital relationship was not a relationship that merges two persons into one, but a relationship that allows two different persons to walk and live together and in harmony. In other words, in a marital relationship, individual aspects and togetherness aspects go hand in hand. Every person in a marital relationship still needs personal space as a space to relate to himself. As such, this personal space was not a space that creates a relationship with a partner a secret relationship, but sometimes a person needs private time to do introspection and reflection. Each married couple in this situation should carefully convey his or her own needs in order to prevent tension in the relationship. Conversely, every couple should be aware that even those who were also married still have the right and necessity of speaking to one another.

4.2 Openness and Protection

Conflict arises between the want to be open in various ways and the desire for not all of them to be open to our partners. Willingness to respond positively to information obtained when dealing with interpersonal interactions. Three facets of interpersonal communication were included in term "openness" attribute. Effective interpersonal communicators should first be receptive to their listeners. This does not imply that the full contents of one's résumé should be made public right away. This might be entertaining, but it frequently hinders communication. On the other side, there should be a willingness to be vulnerable and share information that would be typically kept private, provided that it was appropriate and reasonable to do so. The second aspect refers to the communicator's willingness to react honestly to incoming stimuli. Silent, uncritical, and unresponsive were generally dull communicators. If someone seeks the communicant to react to what the communicator says, the communicator could show openness by reacting spontaneously to other people. The third aspect concerns the ownership of feelings and thoughts where the communicator acknowledges that the feelings and thoughts he expresses were his and he was responsible for them (Avianti & Hendrati, 2011).

Undoubtedly, a successful marriage depends on the quality of communication which may include positivity, openness and trust, which have so far been treated as a means of building the intimacy and support that sustains the relationship. In their notable review, Karney and Bradbury (1995) concluded that distressed and non-distressed marriages could be distinguished in terms of the positive to negative ratio in the relationship (Hou et al., 2018).

Figure 2: Openness and Protection

The 5th couples experiences the dynamics of openness and protection. Husbands were always open about everything, but there were some things that were kept as secrets to maintain harmonious relationships. Husband stated that for him there was no place for Another Ideal

Woman. Therefore, the husband was always open about anyone of the opposite sex who interacts with him. However, sometimes the husband keeps it a secret when the husband and his friends enjoy alcoholic drinks as they know that the wife was very anti-alcohol.

"It's fun, isn't he certain of the characters of his friends, that's how it is. But there were things he wasn't sure about, like drinking, and then he told them about it when it was over. "Oh, you were drinking at the time," I said. But he also told me how he fell" (Interview with Wife 5).

In Jouhari Window's theory, it was clearly stated that in relation to relationships, each person has a space that is known together but also has a space that is secret (Chandra Dewi et al., 2022). Likewise in marital relations, each partner should realize that it was each person right to disclose facts that were known together and keep things secret. The concept of openness was not that everything that is in a person is stated as a fact that is known to others. The concept of openness still respects secret. Given the context, this was a problematic issue in marriage relationships. The couple's marital relationship would be strained if they had so many secrets, but on the other side, everyone needs a place to keep their secrets. The key to determining whether or not this feature of openness and protection would lead to a potential dispute would be the capacity to express this and the understanding that partners have personal rights.

In this situation, the process may determine how effective the communication was. The private space would be smaller the more the lovers comprehend one another and the stronger the quality of their relationship. In other words, something shared knowledge was far more valuable than something secret.

4.3 Novelty and Predictability

While seeking novelty in a relationship, one also has certain expectations. Because dating a new person may not always be enjoyable. The novelty or newness that couple's thought was when they first get married and meet someone with a different character, or when they first start dating or in a relationship before to marriage and encounter new characters who might be different. This necessitates that the partner be knowledgeable about each individual's character. These types of challenges should be met on a daily basis, as well as in facing or resolving issues and hurdles based on prior experience.

The same would be true for other couples; they should adapt to their partners and the environment in which they cohabit, as well as adhere to any agreements made at the outset of the marriage or earlier. When it comes to predictable situations, couples might use their past interactions as a guide for how to treat their spouse since they may use those experiences as a reminder to engage in the necessary action. The best approach to do this was to make heart-to-heart efforts. For instance, when one spouse has a strong attitude, the other partner may anticipate that a strong attitude aimed at him may not achieve positive outcomes. The reference to doing from heart to heart, was an experience that has been obtained by a partner that has been previously possessed, so couples predict using heart to heart would be much better.

Figure 3: Novelty and predictability

The figure above explains that what was related to novelty and predictability in interpersonal relationships in the household was experience and adaptation. Between experience and adaptation go together, where the experience that was owned by a partner could work if the partner could adapt, which means if the partner has a lot of experience regarding individual character then the partner would adjust to take actions that were in accordance with the character of the individual (Nugraha & Maharani, 2017). The harmony of sexual relations and the element of novelty in having sex were experienced by partners 2, 3, 4 and 5. Novelty in having sex could be in the form of variations in having sex or the meaning of sex. According to the findings, couples 2, 3, 4 and 5 were very open in their communication about sexuality. There was a mechanism for discussion and sharing about what they seek in sex. However, this openness of sexual communication was accompanied by an adaptation process so that in the end each one's expectations in sex could be realized.

Marital relations were also a will to build a life together. In other words, there was a necessity to build something new together, be it the perception of shared values or culture of life. The process of building something new would be based on efforts to communicate the will to their partner. Certainly, each individual has a different will. But in a marital relationship, personal will was placed in the context of becoming a common will. This was where the importance of couples builds self-communication. Communicating what he wants to his partner was the beginning of creating a shared will. The common will, however, cannot be developed if there was fear or restriction of the right to express one's will.

4.4 Favoritism and Impartiality

Wish to be treated personally, but on occasion also like to be dealt with in a typical manner. Different conduct was expected during sexual encounters. There has not been a single lady in this entire world who was not designed to be stunning. When women were complimented on their appearance, regardless of their other qualities, they were made to feel unique and special. Certainly not compliments that have a propensity to be corny, even if they were intended solely to make the woman happy. Compliments were all offered in a heartfelt manner. Even in the event that it seems extremely challenging or there were shortcomings that the husband wishes to communicate. Say it in a good way. Avoid being in situations where there were plenty of people or crowds. Feel free to enlighten me as to the errors or omissions. Don't be afraid to offer him some ideas and thoughts so that they might be considered. The same could be said for a woman who was subjected to criticism and comments. Don't give up on it too quickly, even if you don't like it or if you don't feel like yourself when you're doing it.

First, pay attention and engage in what the husband has to say. Take what would be good and leave behind what is not good. As a couple, the husband would always seek to safeguard the woman he loves. Not only partner or girlfriend. Similarly, mothers, sisters, and even friends. It is the husband's responsibility to care for them, both intellectually and physically. Many believe women's freedom entails treating women as husbands treat their guy friends. However, keep in mind that these were women designed to be protected by a husband.

According to study, men genuinely desire the respect of the woman they love. Respect was essential for men. It indicates that he desires to be considered as an important figure in a woman's life. Men appreciate it when the woman they love solicits their input prior to making a decision. Thus, he might feel engaged. The majority of women were easily distrustful of their partners, especially when he has caught with another woman. If you do not trust a man, it implies that you question his devotion to the relationship. If you have any doubts, you should discuss it beforehand rather than hurling it with emotion.

Even if individuals were also extremely busy with work, make time to be with one another. Men do require space and time alone on occasion. However, he also enjoys the quality time they spend together, such as sitting next to him while he watches his favorite soccer team play or jogging with him. Cooperative activities may strengthen relationships. Men were also visual beings, so it is natural for him to appreciate it when his partner makes an effort to look attractive. To make men happy, women don't have to look like a supermodel. They only need to make a small effort to look good in front of him, such as dressing up a bit before you meet him, wearing clothes he likes, or applying attractive perfume.

Men really like it when what they do was appreciated by others, especially by the woman they love. A simple word like "Thank you" means a lot to him. For example, when he treats you to a nice dinner or takes you somewhere, thank him with a smile to show that you appreciate what he has done. Show appreciation for men often, then he will do more for you (Fauziah, 2016).

Figure 4: Favoritism and impartiality

Except for pairs 1 and 5, almost all couples of sources consider something unique about their relationships with their respective partners. Couples 2, focus on quality time for couples. In the middle of a hectic schedule, time spent with family and a partner seems to be a special occasion that strengthens the bond. Sex was considered as a bonus for the 3rd couple in a marriage; consequently, it signifies a particular moment for them and should be explored. Sex has always been discussed with partners in order to enhance the intimacy that would be formed. The fourth

couple makes communication an integral part of their relationship. Consequently, the husband's communication seems to be very intense, even if it occasionally gets excessive. Aside from that, a focus on the significance of communication indicates that the couple's communication was unique and capable of fostering intimacy in the relationship. In marital relationships, communication was not confined to verbal communication but also includes nonverbal communication. The manner in which we treat our partner could be a kind of effective communication. Each individual has to be observant in order to comprehend how his partner wish to be treated.

The way you treat your spouse would be a kind of communication, and like any form of communication, it requires an in-depth recognizing process. There were situations in which one partner does not instantly communicate how he wishes to be treated. The way in which the couple interacts with one another as a channel of communication within their relationship may offer some insight into the nature of the relationship they shared.

4.5 Instrumentality and Affection

Wish to maintain a true relationship, but expect rewards or advantages. No matter how busy your partner was, if he truly loves you, he would attempt to spend time with you. Even though he has a lot on his mind, he always recalls because he takes the time to do things slowly. This also indicates that a romantic relationship was indeed a priority for him. Spending time with your partner might improve relationship harmony. This could be an indication that he prefers everyone to know that he has a partner if he is constantly introducing your partner to his closest relatives and acquaintances. He does not disguise the fact that he is in a relationship and believes that his environment would embrace his partner. Additionally, he seeks to be closer to the people around him so that he might advance to the next level more quickly.

When participants in a relationship did not necessarily place expectations or demands on one another and instead focus on being themselves, the relationship was said to be healthy. If he does willing to accept a whole partner, it is because he is willing to let himself be himself first. When a partner indicates that they were interested in the other person by accepting what would be, it demonstrates that they do not judge the other person's behaviors or actions themselves. When a committed partner would be in a serious relationship, he might consider the future of the relationship. If he has made or discussed future plans that include a partner, you could be confident that he desires a long-term partnership and shared existence.

Figure 5: Instrumentality and affection

When encountering difficulties, many individuals try to isolate themselves and get preoccupied with their own concerns. If your partner has issues and tries to share them with you, this indicates that you were someone who is trusted and respected. Couples attempt to base their

decisions not just on themselves, but also on the other partner, indicating that they appreciate their existence as a partner.

Togetherness was one of the most crucial necessities in a marriage relationship. This togetherness was not only physical, but also psychological. The recognition that one becomes a part of their partner's life was a manifestation of this urge for connection. Every individual requires affection from others. The most important factor in establishing a harmonious relationship is fostering a climate of psychological unity through communication. Being there for important occasions, such as a partner's birthday, or greeting them throughout daily activities was a kind of affection that has a good effect on relationships.

4.6 Equality and Inequality

Sometimes you desire an equal relationship, while other times you desire power. Partners achieve sexual equality by expressing their desires equally. In quality relationships, both parties give and get equally. In other words, neither partner was stronger than the other. Always examine the current state of the relationship. Couples were prohibited from engaging in particular activities. Couples offer the opportunity to make a decision. Couples should constantly adhere to their partner's wishes. If one partner seems dominant, the relationship was considered unequal as each partner has the right to realize his own potential.

A further indicator of a healthy and balanced relationship was mutual support in both good and difficult times, so that couples might motivate one another to become better individuals in the future. A decent companion would respect you and not demand that you conform to the norm. When a couple was able to respect and embrace one another's individuality, it is an indication that they were forming a quality relationship. Additionally, partners should respect the friends and family of other couples, and likewise.

A healthy relationship must be founded on mutual trust. Without mutual confidence, a relationship cannot be successful. There were also occasions when partners hold different views on a topic. Couples should make concessions in order for their relationship to continue running well.

Do not allow the relationship to become tense and full of arguments due to poor communication. Commonplace in the household were little disagreements. The idea might be to communicate truthfully so that there were no miscommunications between spouses. Do not compel your partner to relate a story if he or she seems not prepared to do so.

Figure 6: Equality and inequality

In a healthy relationship, neither party forces the other to engage in sex they did not wish or makes them feel uncomfortable. Relationships based on equality and quality can exist without insulting, belittling, blaming, excessive jealousy, judgment, or physical violence. If the connection contains quality, then these signals of equality should be maintained. But if the situation becomes reversed, the couple should be able to discuss it with their partner. Unhealthy relationships could have negative effects on health. If this occurs, the couple may seek assistance from family, friends, or a psychotherapist, if necessary.

The concept of equality in this relationship was unavailable from the first couple. Husbands were more inclined to be dominant since they saw themselves as a means of subsistence. Therefore, it was discovered in the interview that the wife fears expressing her feelings to her husband. Contrary to the second couple. This couple has an appreciation for the importance of equality in relationships. The sole distinction seems to be the allocation of roles. Consequently, the second couple has very open communication, mutual respect, and no dominance tendencies. Thus, the fifth couple was distinct. Given that she possesses a more reactive personality than her introverted spouse, the wife was considerably more domineering. In interviews, it was shown that husbands wish for their wives to be able to think more generally, as opposed to being reactive and emotionally driven.

Every person desires equality in their relationships. Nonetheless, it should also be acknowledged that, in reality, there is an element of inequality in married relationships based on socioeconomic rank or social duties. Socially, the marriage relationship was inextricable from the social standing and social role of each individual. The disparity in the social position of husbands and wives has become proof of inequality in status and roles. How should this issue be addressed in marriage relationships? It was essential to communicate with your partner in context. When communicating with partners in the context of their separate responsibilities, each individual should respect his partner's role. In the context of interpersonal communication, each individual should respect his partner in the spirit of equality and oneness. In this context, the quality of the couple's relationship was determined by the quality of their communication.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research conducted regarding dialectics in interpersonal relationships between husband and wife, interpersonal relationships are forged to pursue a common goal, mutual benefits, and other advantages. This interpersonal relationship is said to be unique because it contains contradictions or tensions that often occur in interpersonal relationships. The relationship model for husband and wife in building sexual communication relations has the following elements: in terms of autonomy and connection the elements are Autonomy, Care, Duration of communication, Relationship process, Problem Solving, Sharing, and Connection. On the important elements of Openness and Protection, Closedness, Counseling, Persuasive approach, Meeting intensity, Means and Openness. In a relationship want novelty; Novelty (Things that are new), Communication partners, Experience, and Predictable (Things that can be predicted). Wanting to be treated special, but sometimes also wanting to be treated normally, the elements consist of Impartiality, Conflict, Reconciliation, Adaptation and

Favoritism. Wanting to have a sincere relationship, but also expecting benefits or benefits brings out the following elements Instrumentality, Expectation, Interaction and Affection. Sometimes they want equal relations, but sometimes they want to be in power with the important elements of Inequality, Interaction, Conflict, Reconciliation and Equality.

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